

A Proof of Smarandache-Pătrașcu's Theorem using Barycentric Coordinates

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In this article we prove the Smarandache-Pătrașcu's Theorem in relation to the inscribed orthohomological triangles using the barycentric coordinates.

Will remind the following:

Definition

Two triangles ABC and $A_1B_1C_1$, where $A_1 \in BC$, $B_1 \in AC$, $C_1 \in AB$, are called inscribed ortho homological triangles if the perpendiculars in A_1, B_1, C_1 on BC, AC, AB respectively are concurrent.

Observation

The concurrency point P of the perpendiculars on the triangle ABC 's sides from above definition is the orthological center of triangles ABC and $A_1B_1C_1$.

Smarandache-Pătrașcu Theorem

If the triangles ABC and $A_1B_1C_1$ are orthohomological, then the pedal triangle $A'_1B'_1C'_1$ of the second center of orthology of triangles ABC and $A_1B_1C_1$, and the triangle ABC are orthohomological triangles.

Proof

Let $P(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$, $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$, be the first orthologic center of triangles ABC and $A_1B_1C_1$ (See figure).

The perpendicular vectors on the sides are:

$$\mathbf{U}_{BC}^\perp (2a^2, -a^2 - b^2 + c^2, -a^2 + b^2 - c^2)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{CA}^\perp = (-a^2 - b^2 + c^2, 2b^2, a^2 - b^2 - c^2)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{AB}^\perp = (-a^2 + b^2 - c^2, a^2 - b^2 - c^2, 2c^2)$$

We know that:

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{A_1B}}{\overrightarrow{A_1C}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{B_1C}}{\overrightarrow{B_1A}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{C_1A}}{\overrightarrow{C_1B}} = -1 \quad (1)$$

and we want to prove that:

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{A_1'B}}{\overrightarrow{A_1'C}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{B_1'C}}{\overrightarrow{B_1'A}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{C_1'A}}{\overrightarrow{C_1'B}} = -1 \quad (2)$$

We will show that:

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{AB}}{\overrightarrow{AC}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{BC}}{\overrightarrow{BA}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{CA}}{\overrightarrow{CB}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{A_1'B}}{\overrightarrow{A_1'C}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{B_1'C}}{\overrightarrow{B_1'A}} \cdot \frac{\overrightarrow{C_1'A}}{\overrightarrow{C_1'B}} = 1$$

implies the relation (2)

The equation of the line BC is $x=0$, and the equation of the line PA_1 is

$$\begin{vmatrix} 0 & y & z \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ 2a^2 & -a^2 - b^2 + c^2 & -a^2 + b^2 - c^2 \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

It results that:

$$y \cdot \begin{vmatrix} \alpha & \gamma \\ 2a^2 & -a^2 + b^2 + c^2 \end{vmatrix} = z \cdot \begin{vmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ 2a^2 & -a^2 - b^2 + c^2 \end{vmatrix}.$$

Because $y+z=1$, we find:

$$A_1 \left(0, \frac{\alpha}{2a^2} (a^2 + b^2 - c^2) + \beta, \frac{\alpha}{2a^2} (a^2 - b^2 + c^2) + \gamma \right).$$

Similarly:

$$B_1 \left(\frac{-\beta}{2b^2} (-a^2 - b^2 + c^2) + \alpha, 0, \frac{-\beta}{2b^2} (a^2 - b^2 - c^2) + \gamma \right),$$

$$C_1 \left(\frac{-\gamma}{2c^2} (-a^2 + b^2 - c^2) + \alpha, \frac{-\gamma}{2c^2} (a^2 - b^2 - c^2) + \beta, 0 \right)$$

We'll make the following notations:

$$-a^2 + b^2 - c^2 = i; \quad -a^2 - b^2 + c^2 = j, \quad a^2 - b^2 - c^2 = k,$$

And we have:

$$A_1 \left(0, \frac{-\alpha}{2a^2} j + \beta, \frac{-\alpha}{2a^2} i + \gamma \right)$$

$$B_1 \left(\frac{-\beta}{2b^2} j + \alpha, 0, \frac{-\beta}{2b^2} k + \gamma \right)$$

$$C_1 \left(\frac{-\gamma}{2c^2} i + \alpha, \frac{-\gamma}{2c^2} k + \beta, 0 \right)$$

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{A_1 B}}{\overrightarrow{A_1 C}} = -\frac{\frac{-\alpha}{2a^2} i + \gamma}{\frac{-\alpha}{2a^2} j + \beta};$$

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{B_1 C}}{\overrightarrow{B_1 A}} = -\frac{\frac{-\beta}{2b^2} j + \alpha}{\frac{-\beta}{2b^2} k + \gamma};$$

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{C_1 A}}{\overrightarrow{C_1 B}} = -\frac{\frac{-\gamma}{2c^2} k + \beta}{\frac{-\gamma}{2c^2} i + \alpha}$$

If $P'(\alpha', \beta', \gamma')$ is the second center of orthology of the triangles ABC and $A_1 B_1 C_1$, and A'_1, B'_1, C'_1 are the projections of P' on BC , AC , AB respectively, similarly, we'll find:

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{A'_1 B}}{\overrightarrow{A'_1 C}} = -\frac{\frac{-\alpha'}{2a^2} i + \gamma'}{\frac{-\alpha'}{2a^2} i + \beta'};$$

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{B'_1 C}}{\overrightarrow{B'_1 A}} = -\frac{\frac{-\beta'}{2b^2} j + \alpha'}{\frac{-\beta'}{2b^2} k + \gamma'};$$

$$\frac{\overrightarrow{C'_1 A}}{\overrightarrow{C'_1 B}} = -\frac{\frac{-\gamma'}{2c^2} k + \beta'}{\frac{-\gamma'}{2c^2} i + \alpha'}$$

It is known the theorem [2]

Theorem

Given two isogonal conjugated points $P(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ and $P'(\alpha', \beta', \gamma')$ with respect to the triangle ABC ($BC = a$, $CA = b$, $AB = c$), then:

$$\frac{\alpha \alpha'}{a^2} = \frac{\beta \beta'}{b^2} = \frac{\gamma \gamma'}{c^2}.$$

On the other side:

$$\frac{\overline{A_1B}}{\overline{A_1C}} \cdot \frac{\overline{A_1'B}}{\overline{A_1'C}} = \frac{\left(\frac{-\alpha}{2a^2}i + \gamma\right)\left(\frac{-\alpha'}{2a^2}i + \gamma'\right)}{\left(\frac{-\alpha}{2a^2}j + \beta\right)\left(\frac{-\alpha'}{2a^2}j + \beta'\right)} = \frac{\frac{\alpha\alpha'}{4a^4}i^2 - \frac{\alpha\gamma'}{2a^2}i - \frac{\alpha'\gamma}{2a^2}i + \gamma\gamma'}{\frac{\alpha\alpha'}{4a^4}j^2 - \frac{\alpha\beta'}{2a^2}j - \frac{\alpha'\beta}{2a^2}j + \beta\beta'} = \frac{U_1}{V_1},$$

$$\frac{\overline{B_1C}}{\overline{B_1A}} \cdot \frac{\overline{B_1'C}}{\overline{B_1'A}} = \frac{\frac{\beta\beta'}{4b^4}j^2 - \frac{\beta\alpha'}{2b^2}j - \frac{\alpha\beta'}{2b^2}j + \alpha\alpha'}{\frac{\beta\beta'}{4b^4}k^2 - \frac{\beta\gamma'}{2b^2}k - \frac{\beta'\gamma}{2b^2}k + \gamma\gamma'} = \frac{U_2}{V_2},$$

$$\frac{\overline{C_1A}}{\overline{C_1B}} \cdot \frac{\overline{C_1'A}}{\overline{C_1'B}} = \frac{\frac{\gamma\gamma'}{4c^4}k^2 - \frac{\gamma\beta'}{2c^2}k - \frac{\gamma'\beta}{2c^2}k + \beta\beta'}{\frac{\gamma\gamma'}{4c^4}i^2 - \frac{\gamma\alpha'}{2c^2}i - \frac{\gamma'\alpha}{2c^2}i + \alpha\alpha'} = \frac{U_3}{V_3}$$

The only thing left to be proved is that:

$$\frac{U_1}{V_1} \cdot \frac{U_2}{V_2} \cdot \frac{U_3}{V_3} = 1 \text{ if and only if } \frac{a^2}{c^2}U_1 \cdot \frac{b^2}{a^2}U_2 \cdot \frac{c^2}{b^2}U_3 = 1.$$

We show that

$$\frac{b^2}{a^2}U_2 = V_1, \quad \frac{c^2}{b^2}U_3 = V_2, \quad \frac{a^2}{c^2}U_1 = V_3$$

$$\frac{b^2}{a^2}U_2 = \frac{\beta\beta'}{4a^2b^2}j^2 - \frac{\beta\alpha'}{2a^2}j - \frac{\alpha\beta'}{2a^2}j + \frac{b^2}{a^2}\alpha\alpha' = \frac{1}{4a^2} \frac{\alpha\alpha'}{a^2}j^2 - \frac{\beta\alpha'}{2a^2}j - \frac{\alpha\beta'}{2a^2}j + \beta\beta' = V_1$$

$$\frac{c^2}{b^2}U_3 = \frac{\gamma\gamma'}{4c^2b^2}k^2 - \frac{\gamma\beta'}{2b^2}k - \frac{\gamma'\beta}{2b^2}k + \frac{c^2}{b^2}\beta\beta' = \frac{\beta\beta'}{4b^4}k^2 - \frac{\gamma\beta'}{2b^2}k - \frac{\gamma'\beta}{2b^2}k + \gamma\gamma' = V_2$$

$$\frac{a^2}{c^2}U_1 = \frac{\alpha\alpha'}{4a^2c^2}i^2 - \frac{\alpha\gamma'}{2c^2}i - \frac{\alpha'\gamma}{2c^2}i + \frac{a^2}{c^2}\gamma\gamma' = \frac{\gamma\gamma'}{4c^4}i^2 - \frac{\alpha\gamma'}{2c^2}i - \frac{\alpha'\gamma}{2c^2}i + \alpha\alpha' = V_3$$

References

- [1] Ion Pătrașcu and Florentin Smarandache, *A Theorem about Simultaneous Orthological and Homological Triangles*, in [arXiv:1004.0347v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/1004.0347v1), Cornell University, NY, USA, 2010.
- [2] Claudiu Coandă, *Geometrie Analitică în coordonate baricentrice*, Editura Reprograph, Craiova, 2005.
- [3] Mihai Dicu, *The Smarandache-Pătrașcu Theorem of Orthohomological Triangles*, <http://www.scribd.com/doc/28311880/Smarandache-Patrascu-Theorem-of-Orthohomological-Triangles>, 2010.